
CEOS BEST PRACTICE FOR LONG TERM DATA PRESERVATION MANAGEMENT AND CURATION

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Data holdings are growing exponentially in Earth Science data archives worldwide. Only a systematic and standardised approach to data preservation, management and curation during the entire data lifecycle, coordinated between data holders and user communities, will ensure that these data sets will be accessible and useable to current and future generations of users for monitoring long-term variations in environmental parameters as a basis for objectively assessing and predicting the effects of global change. Preservation, management, and curation of Earth observation data and information acquired from space, should be addressed during all phases of Earth observation missions – from the initial mission planning, throughout the entire mission lifetime, and during the post-mission phase.

The Committee on Earth Observation Satellites (CEOS) Working Group on Information Systems and Services (WGISS) has defined a Data Stewardship Reference Lifecycle Model identifying and describing the steps necessary for implementing preservation, management and curation activities on Earth Observation mission data sets from initial conceptualisation through the iterative curation cycle. The Data Stewardship Reference Lifecycle Model describes how data stewardship activities can be efficiently organised and assists data managers with their task of ensuring the long-term preservation, curation, accessibility, discoverability and usability of EO space data sets.

WGISS has in addition produced a set of Best Practices and White Papers to describe in more detail the different Stewardship Reference Model steps and to provide guidance on their technical implementation.

Keywords: Best Practice; Provenance; Data Preservation; Processes; Lifecycle; Data Valorisation

Introduction

This paper presents the CEOS WGISS Best Practice [1] to be applied during the entire Earth observation missions data lifecycle and structured around the Data Stewardship Reference Lifecycle Model which describes the context and how the data stewardship activities can be efficiently organised.

The following Best Practice documents will be introduced and shortly described:

- The *Preservation Workflow Best Practice* [1] assists EO data managers with the task of preparing and facilitating Earth observation space data sets long-term accessibility and usability. Data curation, as part of the overall data stewardship concept, includes data preservation, which is targeted at protecting data integrity and ensuring sustainable accessibility and usability.
- The *Generic EO Data Consolidation Process* [1] provides a series of technical recommendations focused on the implementation of actions for the consolidation of data records and their associated information.
- The *Preserved Data Set Content Best Practice* [1] (used as input to ISO/DIS 19165-2 Geographic information — Preservation of digital data and metadata — Part 2: Content specifications for Earth observation data and derived digital products) gives information on which elements should be preserved together with EO data to ensure their long-term usability and exploitation. The best practice should be tailored for each mission/instrument by involving mission experts and the designated user communities.
- The *Preservation Guidelines* [1] supports the “Detailed Definition” and “Implementation” steps of the Stewardship Reference Model. It contains eight main “themes” consisting of “guiding principles” and a set of “guidelines” that should be applied to guarantee the preservation, accessibility, and usability of EO space data in the long term.

- The *Technical Content and Associated Information Preservation Best Practice* [1] supports data owners in preserving data associated information and tools through a set of recommendations and guidelines.
- The *Persistent Identifiers Best Practice* [1] assists data users with citation and provides recommendations to data providers on the use of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) for Earth Observation data, allowing their globally unique, unambiguous, and permanent identification.
- The *Measuring EO Data Usage Best Practice* [1] contains metrics and indicators usually collected by data owners/providers to gather relevant information on data usage, to generate statistics, stimulate user engagement, and to monitor processes and services. It provides recommended parameters/metrics/indicators to be used, and information to be collected by data providers.

Context and Definitions

The Committee on Earth Observation Satellites (CEOS) Working Group on Information Systems and Services (WGISS) has defined a Data Stewardship Reference Lifecycle Model identifying and describing the steps necessary for implementing preservation, management and curation activities on Earth Observation mission data sets from initial conceptualisation through the iterative curation cycle. The Data Stewardship Reference Lifecycle Model describes how data stewardship activities can be efficiently organised and assists data managers with their task of ensuring the long-term preservation, curation, accessibility, discoverability and usability of EO space data sets.

Data stewardship (Figure 1) implements and verifies, for the relevant data sets, a set of preservation and curation activities on the basis of a set of requirements defined during the initial phase of the curation exercise.

Figure 1 - Content and relationship of concepts within data stewardship

Data preservation activities focus on Earth observation data sets long-term preservation and are tailored according to the mission specific preservation requirements. They consist of all activities required to ensure the “preserved data set” bit integrity over time, its discoverability and accessibility, and to valorise its (re)-use in the long term (e.g. through metadata/catalogue improvement, processor improvement for algorithm and/or auxiliary data changes and related (re)-processing, linking and improvement of context/provenance information, quality assurance). Preservation activities for digital data records acquired by satellites and processed on ground, embrace ensuring continued data records availability, confidentiality, integrity and authenticity as legal evidence to guarantee that data records are not changed or manipulated after generation and reception over the whole continuum of data preservation and curation activities.

Data curation activities aim at establishing and increasing the value of “preserved data sets” over their lifecycle, at favouring their exploitation, possibly through the combination with other data records, and at extending the communities using the data sets. These include activities such as primitive features extraction, exploitation improvement, data mining, and generation of long time data series and collections (e.g. from the same sensor family) in support of specific applications and in cooperation with international partners. Data curation involves annotation, publication and presentation of the data such that their value is maintained over time, and the data remains available for reuse and preservation. Data curation includes "all the processes needed for a controlled data creation, maintenance, and management, together with the capacity to add value to data". In few words the **data curator** task is to facilitate data scientists activities and productivity.

The core target of the Data Stewardship lifecycle is the preserved data set, composed of consolidated:

- **Data records:** these include raw data, Level 0 data and higher-level products, browse images, auxiliary and ancillary data, calibration and validation data sets, metadata and descriptive information.
- **Technical Content and Associated Information:** this includes all the processing software used in the product generation, quality control, the product visualisation and value adding tools, and documentation needed to make the data records understandable to the designated community. This includes information on the mission operation concept, product specifications, instrument characteristics, algorithm descriptions, Cal/Val procedures, mission/instrument performance reports, quality related information, etc. technical content and associated information is necessary to ensure data remains understandable and usable in time.

Data Stewardship Reference Lifecycle

Earth Science data curation and preservation should be addressed during all mission stages - from the initial mission planning, throughout the entire mission lifetime, and during the post-mission phase. The Data Stewardship Reference Lifecycle Model (Figure 2) provides a high-level overview of the steps needed to implement curation and preservation actions on mission data sets through an iterative cycle.

Figure 2 - Data Stewardship Reference Lifecycle Model

Figure 3 shows the applicability phase of each Best Practice described in this document (plus a series of additional documents produced by WGISS and available on the CEOS web site).

WGISS ASSETS	Initialization	Detailed Definition	Implementation	Operations & Maintenance
Best Practices and White Paper				
EO Data Glossary of Acronyms and Terms	▲			▲
Preservation Workflow	▲			▲
EO Data Preservation Guidelines	▲			
Preserved Data Set Content	▲			
Generic EO Data Set Consolidation Process	▲			▲
CEOS Persistent Identifiers Best Practices				▲
CEOS Associated knowledge Preservation Best Practices	▲	▲		▲
EO Data Purge Alert Procedure				▲
WGISS Data Management and Stewardship Maturity Matrix	▲	▲	▲	▲
Measuring of Earth Observation Data Usage	▲	▲		
WGISS DSIG Browse Guidelines Document images	▲	▲		
CEOS OpenSearch Documentation		▲		
CWIC Documentation		▲		
IDN Documentation		▲		
FedEO Documentation		▲		
FDA Documentation	▲	▲		
WGISS Connected Data Assets Metrics		▲		

Figure 3 – WGISS Best Practices Applicability Phase

Preservation Workflow

The data stewardship reference lifecycle is also represented through the preservation workflow, which defines a recommended set of actions to be sequentially implemented for the preservation of a “data set”, with the goal of ensuring and optimising its (re)-use in the long term. This preservation workflow, collaboratively developed with international space data holders, aims at ensuring that Earth observation mission data sets remain accessible and useable in the long term. Workflow application will produce a consolidated, accessible and useable Earth observation data set – consisting of the data records and associated technical content and information. While best initiated during the early mission planning phases, the preservation workflow can also be applied to data sets of current and historic Earth observation missions. The preservation workflow consists of four phases:

- *Initialisation (preservation planning)*
- *Consolidation*
- *Implementation*
- *Operations*

Figure 4 – Preservation Workflow

The preservation workflow defines a procedure which consists of the set of actions preferably but not necessarily to be conducted in sequence. The output of applying the procedure will be a complete, discoverable, accessible, and useable Earth observation data set, including the data records and the associated information, and a series of documents describing the preservation strategy pursued, the implementation plan, and individual activities conducted.

Generic EO Data Consolidation Process

The Generic EO Data Consolidation Process [1] focuses on the consolidation of the Data Records and their Associated Information. The data record type covered by this process is potentially any data record including raw data, Level 0 data and higher-level products, browse images, auxiliary and ancillary data, calibration and validation data sets, and metadata. The Consolidation Process is composed of the following recommended steps:

- *Step 1:* Data set analysis and collection – assessment and collection of input data and transcription of unique data from media (if any).

- *Step 2:* Cleaning/pre-processing – Data set cleaning and production of a master data set which is devoid of corrupted and duplicate files, aligned to the same naming convention and file format.
- *Step 3:* Completeness analysis – Analysis of mission data set completeness to identify potential gaps and define recovery activities.
- *Step 4:* Processing/reprocessing – Regarding Level 0 data, this step consists of the regeneration of any missing or erroneous L0 product from raw data or L0 unconsolidated data. Regarding higher level products, full processing is usually performed to generate all planned product types whilst reprocessing campaigns are carried-out when deemed necessary (e.g. to fill identified gaps, or if a new algorithm/processor becomes available).

Figure 5 – Consolidation Process Steps

Preserved Data Set Content (PDSC) Best Practice

This Best Practice identifies the detailed EO mission dataset content (i.e. data records and associated information) that should be preserved to ensure long-term usability and exploitation of Earth Science data. It is intended to assist data managers in making sure that the recommended and mandatory content is collected and certified for completeness and quality, and provides the list of expected documents, content and quality information to be generated and preserved at each of the following mission stages:

1. Mission Concept (MC). Defines the mission to a sufficient level to show the scientific value and technical feasibility. During this stage, identification of the science requirements by the Science study team and study scientist are carried out. Additional activities include the identification of a reference platform to be used in the preliminary system level studies. Feasibility verification documents, mission technology and programmatic estimates for the future mission stages are also generated.
2. Mission Definition (MD). This stage is concerned with the mission scientific requirements detailed definition and the selection of technical solutions for system concept. During this stage, types of scientific instrument measurements (e.g. spectral analysis, temperature measurement, etc.) are identified and defined eventually combining existing sensors/instruments in different modes or with different scientific models.
3. Mission Implementation (MI). According to Mission Definition results, this stage produces the detailed definition and implementation of the mission system and components: sensors/instruments; algorithms and their relationship in the frame of scientific domains; methods of measurement and any other context necessary to perform measures. Production, development testing and pre-qualification of selected critical elements and components lead to the conclusion of the technology development activities.
4. Mission Operations (MO). This stage identifies the operational timeframe of the mission being the period during which data are captured, algorithms are revised and improved, activities concerned with input analysis, calibration and validation of sensor/instrument as well as activities concerned with qualification of processed data are performed.
5. Post Mission (PM). This represents the Post-Operations and Preservation stages which mainly focus on the archived data to accommodate the need to preserve them in the long term for further reuse and exploitation. The post mission stage starts with the satellite end of life (e.g.

for an Earth Observation mission with the event of satellite disposal or failure). The Post Mission stage focuses on datasets (data and information) consolidation and appraisal, datasets reprocessing to align to the latest version, ground segment and media disposal (depending on specific mission), and data and associated information migration to a long-term preservation environment. During the Post Mission stage, a limited set of functions (e.g. data discovery and access) is provided by the mission ground segment (still in operation) according to the adopted strategy and depending on mission requirements until its disposal and data migration to long-term preservation. This stage also focuses on historical data reuse and exploitation, on data and concerned information preservation against aging and technological changes, and on data curation and enrichment).

The PDSC Best Practice should be tailored appropriately for each specific mission/instrument with the involvement of mission experts and the designated user communities. Procedures must be in place to ensure that all data quality information identified in the PDSC is traceable and preserved. The PDSC Best Practice has been also used as input to the definition of the “ISO/DIS 19165-2 Geographic information — Preservation of digital data and metadata — Part 2: Content specifications for earth observation data and derived digital products” standard.

Preservation Guidelines

The Preservation Guidelines document [1] covers and supports the Initialization (planning) and Implementation steps of the Preservation Workflow [1]. The guidelines and the underlying data preservation approach should be applied to heritage, current and future Earth Observation missions data sets. The document addresses technical and organisational aspects for the long-term preservation of EO data and includes security, accessibility and usability aspects, recommending applicable standards and procedures. It is structured around eight main “themes” consisting of “guiding principles” and a set of “guidelines” that should be applied to guarantee the preservation, accessibility, and usability of EO space data in the long term. The eight themes are the following:

1. Preserved data set content definition and appraisal
2. Archive operations and organisation
3. Archive security
4. Data ingestion
5. Archive maintenance
6. Data access and interoperability
7. Data exploitation and re-processing
8. Data purge prevention

Technical Content and Associated Information Preservation Best Practice

Digital Preservation represents the management and maintenance of digital objects so they can be accessed and used by future users. The main purpose of this document is to help data owners in preserving information and tools through the application of a set of recommendations and guidelines. The Technical Content and Associated Information preservation best practice is strictly related to the PDSC Best Practice and needs to be tailored for the specific mission, taking into consideration the user community needs, cost / benefit analysis, preservation objectives, Intellectual Propriety Rights (IPR), and other dependencies. Once tailored for the specific mission, the document can be used by applying the recommended approach for the preservation of the identified technical content and information. The recommended preservation formats for Information Preservation are listed below (excerpt):

- Text documents (often MS Word, Excel Files, txt, etc.) can be preserved as: PostScript, PDF/A, DSSSL, RTF, ASCII, SGML, TIFF, CGM
- Images (JPEG, TIFF, PNG, FITS, etc.) can be preserved as: Loss of Quality JPEG, JPEG2000 Lossless compression TIFF, PBM, PNG, FITS.
- Metadata (ASCII, XML, SGML, etc.) can be preserved as: ASCII, the most durable format for metadata because it is widespread, backwards compatible when used with Unicode (superset of ASCII), and utilises human-readable characters, not numeric codes. For higher functionality, SGML or XML should be used.
- Multimedia (AVI, QuickTime, MPEG, WMV, MJ2) can be preserved as: MJ2, MPEG-A, Mp4.
- Physical (3D) can be preserved as: Scan 3D format.

Persistent Identifiers Best Practice

The growth of scientific and non-scientific digital data is resulting in an increasing number of digital objects and resources that have to be managed. This data intensive environment offers many new opportunities: the possibility of accessing a massive amount of scientific and cultural data in digital format, the increasing linkage across authors and their publications, the development of new and much more powerful metrics for assessing the impact of scientific productions, etc. However, this scenario has led to the emergence of new challenges such as digital preservation, data integration, quality assessment and provenance. These challenges become magnified in global contexts where resources are distributed across systems and standards, and the movement of data across disciplines and organisations is very intensive.

The main purpose of the Persistent Identifiers Best Practice is to help data providers in ensuring unique identification of their datasets (with related benefits in terms of data integrity and provenance), and users in citing and finding specific data sets. The document describes the state-of-the-art for what concerns PIDs technologies and provides a set of use cases and guidelines concerning their implementation for EO mission data, allowing globally unique, unambiguous, and permanent identification of a space digital object for locating and accessing it over time.

Figure 6 – Information flows in a PID system

Measuring EO Data Usage Best Practice

Measurement of EO data usage and impact is fundamental for EO data providers. In the past, this was a relatively straightforward process with, most often, a direct, one-to-one relationship between the data provider and the data user, which facilitated a detailed knowledge regarding the use of data. Evolution of the EO ecosystem and data access paradigm, led to the proliferation of one-to-many data dissemination systems and large and diverse cloud-based data sources from data owners and redistributors. In this changing environment, where the data providers can be separated from the data user by several intermediaries, some measurements or metrics of both how and how much data is being used become critical in providing the necessary feedback to data providers and funding entities.

Metrics and indicators have been historically collected by data owners/providers to gather relevant information on data usage, to generate statistics, stimulate user engagement, and to monitor processes and services. In the past, data providers were performing this independently, without coordination. Today, the evolving landscape in Earth Observation (EO) data usage, with the arrival of new technologies and the Big Data paradigm (e.g. bringing users to the data as a complementary approach to data download) allows for more powerful statistics and analysis. This document provides recommended parameters/metrics/indicators to be used, together with relevant information to be collected by data providers, in order to measure objectives and needs expressed by the organisation.

Conclusion

Data holdings are growing exponentially in Earth Science data archives worldwide. Only a systematic and standardised approach to data preservation, management and curation during the entire data lifecycle, coordinated between data holders and user communities, will ensure that these data sets will be accessible and useable to current and future generations of users for monitoring long-term variations in environmental parameters as a basis for objectively assessing and predicting the effects of global

change. Preservation, management, and curation of Earth observation data and information acquired from space, should be addressed during all phases of Earth observation missions – from the initial mission planning, throughout the entire mission lifetime, and during the post-mission phase. In the frame of CEOS WGISS the main objective of the Data Preservation and Stewardship Interest Group is to draft common cross-agency best practices or guidelines of data stewardship for possible adoption by the interested organisation. All best practices [1] can be accessed freely and openly on the CEOS web site (<https://ceos.org/ourwork/workinggroups/wgiss/preservation/>)

References

[1] CEOS Best Practices

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